

Studies on Some Phenanthraphenazines*

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Synthesis of twentyone phenanthraphenazines, one of which is green have been described. These compounds are likely to be biologically active.

Although Witt prepared a dyestuff in 1886 by the action of 1 : 2 : 4-triaminobenzene on phenanthraquinone¹, it was only in the nineteen twenties when a few substituted phenanthraquinones were condensed with a few *o*-diamines^{2,3}. Later Dutta and co-worker⁴ synthesised some phenanthraphenazines carrying substituents in the benzene moiety (position 1 to 4). Their colour range between yellow and red, while two of them are reported to be black but they impart a 'green-brown' colour to wool.

In connection with investigation of natural products, a number of 9 . 10-phenanthraquinones and their phenanthraphenazines have been prepared. However, a very large majority of these phenanthraphenazines, carry substituents in the phenanthrene skeleton only.

Rudali *et al*⁵ have studied the carcinogenic activity of some phenanthraphenazines. Neoplasm was observed by them in more than 50% of the test cases. Anti-tumor activity of some derivatives of phenanthraphenazines have also been observed⁶.

It was expected that the preparation of a number of phenanthraphenazines with substituents in the benzene moiety (position 1 to 4) and carrying substituents in the phenanthrene residue, may lead to the production of deep coloured dyes. In fact, this hope has been partially realised, in so far as amongst others, a green dye has now been obtained.

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TABLE
OP-*ortho*phenylenediamine

Sl. No.	PQ = Phenanthraquinone Name	Reactants	Appearance; Solvent	M.P. °C (Yield %) crude	Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular formula	Analysis	
							Found	Reqd.
<i>Section I</i>								
1.	1-Chlorophenanthraphenazine	PQ + 3-Chloro-OP	Light yellow long needles Benzene.	232 (89)	Intense purple	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₂	N	9.0 8.9
2.	1-Chloro (or 4-Chloro)-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine	2-Nitro-PQ + 3-chloro-OP	Lemon yellow granules Benzene, si	243 (78)	Deep reddish brown.	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂	N	11.6 11.7
3.	1-Chloro-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 3-chloro-OP	Yellow lky needles Nitrobenzene	367 (94)	Deep orange	C ₂₀ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄	N	13.9 13.8
<i>Section II</i>								
4.	1-Bromophenanthraphenazine	PQ + 3-Bromo-OP	Light green needles Benzene.	235-36 (83.5)	Deep reddish- purple	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ BrN ₂	N C H	7.8 66.7 2.8 7.8 66.8 2.7
5.	1-Bromo (or 4-Bromo)-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine	2-Nitro-PQ + 3-bromo-OP.	Light yellow granules Benzene.	248 (66)	Deep amber	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ BrN ₃ O ₂	N	10.6 10.4
6.	1-Bromo-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 3-bromo-OP.	Yellow silky needles Nitrobenzene	above 380 (66.7)	Deep red	C ₂₀ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₄	N	12.6 12.5
<i>Section III</i>								
7.	1-Iodophenanthraphenazine	PQ + 3-Iodo-OP	Lemon yellow granules Ethylacetate.	219-20 (82.7)	Deep blood red.	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ I ₁ N ₂	N	7.0 6.9
8.	1-Iodo (or 4-Iodo)-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine	2-Nitro-PQ + 3-iodo-OP	Yellow needles Benzene	229-30 (74.4)	Deep brownish red.	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ I ₁ N ₃ O ₂	N	9.4 9.3
9.	1-Iodo-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 3-iodo-OP.	Yellow silky needles Nitrobenzene.	above 365 (70.5)	Brown	C ₂₀ H ₉ I ₁ N ₄ O ₄	N	11.4 11.3

TABLE—Contd.

Sl. No.	Name	Reactants	Appearance; Solvent	M.P. °C (Yield %) crude	Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular formula	Analysis	
							Found	Reqd.
<i>Section IV</i>								
10.	2-Methoxyphenanthraphenazine	PQ + 4-Methoxy-OP	Light yellow granules	192-95 (84)	Deep pink	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	N 9.3	9.0
11.	2-Methoxy (or 3-Methoxy)-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine.	2-Nitro-PQ + 4-methoxy-OP.	Acetic acid. Lemon yellow granules	236-38 (99)	Intense pink	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	N 11.7	11.8
12.	2-Methoxy-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine.	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 4-methoxy-OP.	Nitrobenzene. Dirty yellow granules Pyridine.	325 (30)	Deep pink	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅	N 14.1	14.0
<i>Section V</i>								
13.	2 : 3-Dimethylphenanthra-phenazine.	PQ + 4 : 5-Dimethyl-OP.	Yellow shining needles	289 (93)	Deep purple	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂	N 9.0	9.1
14.	2 : 3-Dimethyl-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine.	2-Nitro-PQ + 4 : 5-dimethyl-OP	Benzene. Yellow silky needles	302-03 (80)	Deep red	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	N 12.0	11.9
15.	2 : 3-Dimethyl-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine.	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 4 : 5-dimethyl-OP	Nitrobenzene. Deep yellow needles	366-67 (75)	Deep bright orange red.	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄	N 14.2	14.1
<i>Section VI</i>								
16.	2 : 3-Dichlorophenanthra-phenazine.	PQ + 4 : 5-Dichloro-OP	Lemon yellow needles	262-63 (88.6)	Pink	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂	N 7.5	8.0
17.	2 : 3-Dichloro-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine.	2-Nitro-PQ + 4 : 5-dichloro-OP	Benzene. Lemon yellow granules	294 (71.5)	Deep pink	C ₂₀ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	N 10.5	10.7
18.	2 : 3-Dichloro-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine.	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 4 : 5-dichloro-OP	Nitrobenzene. Yellow granules	382 (59)	Deep scarlet red.	C ₂₀ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄	N 12.7	12.8
<i>Section VII</i>								
19.	2 : 4-Dibromophenanthra-phenazine.	PQ + 4 : 6-Dibromo-OP	Deep yellow silky needles	251 (86.5)	Intense pink	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂	N 6.6	6.4
20.	2 : 4-Dibromo- (or 1 : 3-Dibromo)-12-nitrophenanthraphenazine.	2-Nitro-PQ + 4 : 6-dibromo-OP	Benzene. Yellow granules	249-51 (64.5)	Intense blood red	C ₂₀ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	N 8.8	8.7
21.	2 : 4-Dibromo-7 : 12-dinitrophenanthraphenazine.	2 : 7-Dinitro-PQ + 4 : 6-dibromo-OP	Deep lemon yellow granules	338-39 (75.4)	Deep orange red.	C ₂₀ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄	N 10.9	10.6

The phenanthraphenazines, reported herein have been obtained, by the condensation of 9 : 10-phenanthraquinone, 2-nitro-9 : 10-phenanthraquinone and 2 : 7-dinitro-9 : 10-phenanthraquinone with seven different diamines, e.g., 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, 3-iodo-, 4-methoxy-, 4 : 5-dimethyl-, 4 : 5-dichloro-, 4 : 6-dibromo-*o*-phenylenediamines.

The condensations, obviously, lead to the possibility of alternative structures for five of the several phenanthraphenazines described. The alternative possibilities and other details have been recorded in the table.

The phenanthraphenazines are, in general, of yellow shade and curiously, one of them, 1-bromo-phenanthraphenazine has a green colour although the shade is light or pale (serial no. 4). Its benzene solution shows marked violet fluorescence. Repeated chromatography shows that the compound is homogeneous. The compound dyes wool a light green yellow shade and absorbs maximally at 612 nm and at 562 nm.

These phenanthraphenazines will be shortly screened for biological activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following general procedure was adopted :

To a hot solution of the phenanthraquinone in acetic acid was added a solution of the diamine in warm acetic acid and the mixture was refluxed for a short time to ensure complete reaction. The precipitated product was removed by filtration and crystallised several times to get pure compound.

In column chromatography aluminium oxide was used. TLC was carried out in benzene-chloroform mixture (50 : 50) using iodine as the visualising agent. Single spot was obtained, R_f value 0.7. Similar result was obtained from pet. ether-chloroform (50 : 50) solvent.

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